

AI AND RENAISSANCE POETRY

HOW PROMPT LANGUAGE SHAPES LITERARY TRANSLATION

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1 INTRODUCTION

This study explores how Large Language Models perform in the translation of literary texts, focusing on Renaissance Italian poetry.

It investigates whether prompt language (Italian vs English) influences translation strategies and output quality.

2 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- Can AI translate archaic texts with stylistic solutions comparable to those of a human expert?
- How does prompt language influence translation outcomes?

3 METHODOLOGY

Case study: Petrarch's sonnet "Erano i capei d'oro a l'aura sparsi" (vv. 1-4)

Comparison:

- AI - Deepseek (Italian prompt)
- AI - Deepseek (English prompt)
- Gold standard (Joseph Tusiani)

Evaluation criteria:

- Semantic fidelity
- Use of Imagery
- Rhythm & musicality
- Metric / Structural Coherence
- Stylistic Naturalness

4 CASE STUDY

Petrarch Original	Erano i capei d'oro a l'aura sparsi
TUSIANI Gold Standard	Loose in the Breeze, the gold of all her hair was in a thousand playful ringlets blown
ITALIAN PROMPT Example output	Her golden hair was spread to the breeze, which in a thousand sweet knots it entwined
ENGLISH PROMPT Example output	Her golden hair streamed loose to Zephyr's play , In countless sweet coils by the breeze entwined

5 EVALUATION RESULTS

Aspect	IT Prompt	EN Prompt	Tusiani
Semantic Fidelity	★★★★☆	★★★★☆☆	★★★★★★
Use of Imagery	★★★☆☆	★★★★★☆☆	★★★★★★
Rhythm & musicality	★★★★☆☆	★★★★☆☆	★★★★★★
Metric/ Structural Coherence	★★★★☆☆	★★★★★☆☆	★★★★★★
Stylistic Naturalness	★★★★☆☆	★★★★★☆☆	★★★★★★

★★★★★★ Excellent ★★★★★☆☆ Good ★★★★☆☆☆☆ Fair
★★★☆☆☆☆ Poor ★★☆☆☆☆☆☆ Very poor

The full comparative analysis is available here:

6 KEY INSIGHTS

Prompt language significantly shapes translation strategy.

Italian prompts tend to preserve semantic structure, while English prompts encourage more adaptive and stylistically creative outputs..

AI can support literary translation, but poetic structure and stylistic nuance remain difficult to reproduce consistently.

7 CONCLUSION

AI can support literary translation, but poetic rhythm, stylistic nuance, and interpretative depth still require human sensitivity and cultural empathy.

8 NEXT STEPS

- Comparative analysis of additional Renaissance texts and dialectal varieties
- Cross-model comparison across DeepSeek, Gemini, Claude and DeepL
- Further analysis of rhythm and metrical adaptation through Spanish and French prompts

REFERENCES

- Petrarch, *Rerum vulgarium fragmenta*, sonnet LXIX
- Tusiani, Joseph: "Italian Poets of the Renaissance", 1971, Baroque Press Inc, Long Island City, N.Y.
- Jeremy Munday. *Introducing Translation Studies: Theories and Applications*. London/New York: Routledge, 2012.
- Lea, Gary R. "Constructivism and Its Risks in Artificial Intelligence." *Prometheus* 36, no. 4 (2020): 322-346.

AI IS A POWERFUL TOOL, BUT PROMPTING MAKES THE DIFFERENCE
PROMPT WITH CARE. TRANSLATE WITH INSIGHT